

Thermodynamic Functions of Ionisation of Benzoic and Substituted Benzoic Acids in Dioxan-Water Mixtures

UPENDRA N. DASII

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar-751 004

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Free energies of transfer of benzoic and of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted nitro-, chloro-, hydroxy- and aminobenzoic acids from water to dioxan-water mixtures have been estimated from thermodynamic ionisation constants. ${}^1pK_a^m$ of these acids obtained from the electromotive force measurements of buffer cells. The effect of the substituents on the ${}^1pK_a^m$ of benzoic acid has been discussed in these mixed solvents in terms of qualitative theory of substituent effects.

Ionisation constants and the thermodynamics for acid-base equilibria in solvents comprising binary aqueous mixtures are helpful in understanding the solvent effects. The study on the ion-solvent interactions in dioxan-water mixtures is reported for a number of mono- and dicarboxylic acids^{1,2} Dash *et al.*³ also reported the thermodynamics of the substituted acids and the linear free energy relationships in a wide variety of non-aqueous and of binary aqueous mixtures.

In order to provide an insight into the solvation of benzoate ions in water-dioxan mixtures, the ionisation constants of benzoic and substituted benzoic acids have been evaluated at five different temperatures (15–35°) and in four different compositions of dioxan (10, 20, 30 and 40%, w/w)-water mixtures from the electromotive force measurements of the cells of type.

where HX is the benzoic or substituted benzoic acid and KX is the corresponding potassium salt

Calculations The method of calculation of the ionisation constant (K_a^m) was similar to those recommended by Harned and Owen for moderately weak acids³. The 'apparent' hydrogen ion molality (m_{H^+}) is related to the e.m.f. of cell (A) by the equation^{4,5},

$$\begin{aligned} -\log m_{\text{H}^+}' &= \frac{(\Delta E)F}{2 \cdot 3026RT} + \log m_3 + 2 \log \gamma_{\pm} \\ &= \frac{(\Delta E)F}{2 \cdot 3026RT} + \log m_3 + \frac{2\Lambda(I d_0)^{1/2}}{1 + B a^0 (I d_0)^{1/2}} \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

where, $\Delta E = E - E^\circ$, E is the observed e.m.f. of the cell (A), E° the standard e.m.f. of the cell. $\text{H}_2(1 \text{ atm})/\text{HCl}(m)/\text{AgCl(s), Ag(s)}$ and m_3 the molality of KCl solution. The ionic strength (I) is given by

$$I = m_2 + m_3 + m_{\text{H}^+}'$$

The values of I and m_{H^+}' were calculated as described earlier⁶. The 'apparent' ionisation constant (K_a^m) can be calculated from the expression^{4,5},

$$\log K_a^m = -\frac{2A(I d_0)^{1/2}}{1 + B a^0 (I d_0)^{1/2}} + \log \frac{m_{\text{H}^+}'(m_2 + m_{\text{H}^+}')}{(m_1 - m_{\text{H}^+}')} \quad (2)$$

where, m_1 and m_2 are the molalities of the acid and its potassium salt respectively. d_0 is the density of the solvent concerned. A and B are the Debye-Hückel constants and a^0 is the ion-size parameter of the acid. The true (thermodynamic) ionisation constant (K_a^m) was obtained from the intercept of the plot of $\log K_a^m$ versus the ionic strength. The values of the e.m.f. of the cell (A) were measured with different solutions from $m_1 = 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$, $m_2 = 0.8 \times 10^{-2}$ and $m_3 = 0.9 \times 10^{-2}$ upto $m_1 = 1.4 \times 10^{-2}$, $m_2 = 1.1 \times 10^{-2}$ and $m_3 = 9.5 \times 10^{-2}$ mol kg⁻¹. The ionic strength of the solution in the cell was varied in the range $(1.8-10.8) \times 10^{-2}$ mol kg⁻¹.

The values of E° of the silver-silver chloride electrode in various compositions of dioxan-water mixtures were obtained from the literature⁶. The values of d_0 and the Debye-Hückel constants (A and B) were also obtained from the literature^{4,7} or calculated in molal

scale by usual methods. The e.m.f. values obtained from the cell (A) were corrected to 1 atmosphere⁸. For the suitable choice of the ion-size parameter (a^0) the ionisation constants of the acids at 25° were calculated for various values of a^0 in the range of 0.25–0.6 nm^{1,6} at an interval of 0.05 nm following the same principle as adopted by Roy *et al.*⁹. Since a^0 is almost insensitive to temperature^{8,10}, we sought a single value of a^0 which would satisfy the whole body of data of the corresponding acid over the temperature range 15–35°. Any possible error in the value of pK_a^m due to deviations from the Debye-Hückel equation in the experimental conditions was compensated by the extrapolation method used and the adjustment of the parameter a^0 in our calculation procedure. The values of pK_a^m obtained from the linear extrapolation of pK_a^m to $I = 0$ in the dioxan-water mixtures at different temperatures were fitted by a least-squares method to an equation recommended by Harned and Robinson¹¹,

$$pK_a^m = A/T + B + C T \quad (3)$$

The parameters A , B and C for pK_a^m of the acids in different solvents are recorded in Table 1. The average deviations between the observed values of pK_a^m and those calculated from equation (3) are within the range 0.003–0.006 log unit. Using these parameters, the various thermodynamic quantities for the ionisation process of the acids in their standard states have been evaluated from the equations,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^0 &= 2.3026 R (A + BT + CT^2) \\ \Delta H^0 &= 2.3026 R (A - CT^2) \\ \Delta S^0 &= -2.3026 R (B + 2CT) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

These quantities at 25° are presented in Table 2 along with those in aqueous medium¹². Table 2 also includes the pK_a^m values of these acids in water¹² and dioxan-water mixtures at 25°.

The standard Gibbs free energy change for the transfer process associated with the ionisation of acids between water (w) and mixed solvents (s) of various compositions has been computed from the relation.

$$\Delta G_t^0(N) = 2.3026 R T ({}_s pK_a(N) - {}_w pK_a(N)) \quad (5)$$

where, $pK_a(N) = pK_a^m + 2 \log(1000/M)$, and M is the average molecular weight of the solvent concerned, and m and N represent the molal and mol-fraction scales

respectively. ΔG_t^0 is usually expressed in mol-fraction scale in order to eliminate any change in it due to concentration change. The values of ΔH_t^0 and ΔS_t^0 (in mol-fraction scale) may be computed from the usual relations.

Results and Discussion

As observed from Table 2, pK_a^m values are higher in dioxan-water mixtures compared to those in water and tend to increase with increasing dioxan content as expected. The magnitude of the increase is in accordance with the electrostatic charging (Born) effect corresponding to the monotonic increase of D^{-1} (reciprocal of dielectric constant) or the composition of dioxan-water mixtures. The relative strength of the acids in the mixed solvents are found to be the same as that in aqueous medium. Similar observations have been reported on benzoic acids in water-methanol, -ethanol, -1-propanol, -2-propanol, -glycerol, -D-glucose and -D-fructose mixtures³. The effect of substituents on the ionisation process of the carboxylic group in the mixed solvents appears to be in complete agreement with the qualitative theory of substituent effects.

A comparison of the present data of the thermodynamic quantities for the ionisation of the acids with the corresponding values in water is difficult because of lack of relevant data in water for all acids used in the present study. However, the available data for the ΔG^0 values at 25° for all the acids in water show that there is a steady increase in ΔG^0 values among the isomers with a given substituent and also among the acids of related structure with solvent composition. The increase is linear and in accordance with the electrostatic charging effect as just discussed. By making the comparison of ΔH^0 values available in water at 25° for benzoic, *meta*- and *para*-substituted nitro- and chlorobenzoic and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acids, there seems no consistent form of behaviour in ΔH^0 throughout the set of acids and solvents. However, the positive magnitude of the ΔH^0 values both in water (except for *m*-chlorobenzoic acid) and dioxan-water mixed solvents indicates similar pattern of solvation in these media. The ionisation process is more energy consuming (excepting *o*-hydroxybenzoic acid in all solvents and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid in water-rich solvents) in the mixed solvents than in pure water as evident from the higher

ΔH^0 values in the former solvents

The standard entropy of ionisation is negative in both water and dioxan-water mixed solvents, and in dioxan-rich solvents this seems to be more negative than in water. This may be due to the fact that the degree of reorientation and partial immobilisation of the

dioxan and water molecules by H^+ ion and carboxylate ion are greater in dioxan-rich solvents than in pure water. As observed the variation of ΔS^0 with solvent composition is monotonic and consistent in form throughout the set of acids and solvents. The difference in magnitude of the ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values in these

TABLE I - CONSTANTS OF EQUATION (3) FOR THE ACIDS IN DIOXAN-WATER MIXTURES

Acid	Constants	Wt % dioxan			
		10	20	30	40
Benzoic	<i>f</i>	374.53	68.38	222.52	75.54
	<i>B</i>	2.397	4.588	4.016	5.424
	$C \times 10^3$	2.606	0.956	1.218	0.334
<i>o</i> -Nitro-	<i>f</i>	324.02	13.20	141.97	304.10
	<i>B</i>	0.406	2.564	2.340	1.665
	$C \times 10^3$	2.315	1.092	0.178	2.128
<i>m</i> -Nitro-	<i>f</i>	53.26	577.25	337.43	293.36
	<i>B</i>	4.451	0.258	2.467	3.302
	$C \times 10^3$	2.119	5.188	2.485	1.788
<i>p</i> -Nitro-	<i>f</i>	95.90	279.86	66.90	263.88
	<i>B</i>	3.118	5.719	1.794	3.067
	$C \times 10^3$	0.316	4.477	1.771	1.792
<i>o</i> -Chloro-	<i>f</i>	443.05	121.86	17.21	126.42
	<i>B</i>	0.709	3.0	4.605	5.685
	$C \times 10^3$	3.752	0.1	1.808	2.687
<i>m</i> -Chloro-	<i>f</i>	9.83	50.04	16.02	402.59
	<i>B</i>	4.247	4.624	4.962	2.643
	$C \times 10^3$	1.495	1.728	1.261	3.303
<i>p</i> -Chloro-	<i>f</i>	616.36	131.37	33.48	533.22
	<i>B</i>	0.245	5.350	4.802	8.985
	$C \times 10^3$	5.593	2.783	0.821	6.956
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy-	<i>f</i>	110.01	463.16	283.21	614.73
	<i>B</i>	4.147	0.431	3.260	9.695
	$C \times 10^3$	2.567	3.772	1.650	1.9
<i>m</i> -Hydroxy-	<i>f</i>	182.15	110.26	161.83	38.69
	<i>B</i>	5.899	3.992	4.270	5.974
	$C \times 10^3$	3.375	0.064	0.524	1.425

Table - 1 (contd)

<i>p</i> -Hydroxy-	A	171.07	59.30	105.14	178.62
	B	3.969	5.618	5.102	5.157
	$C \times 10^3$	0.688	1.908	0.051	0.428
<i>o</i> -Amino-	A	124.76	321.52	50.90	261.68
	B	4.634	3.436	6.589	8.436
	$C \times 10^3$	0.288	2.427	1.965	4.278
<i>m</i> -Amino-	A	430.39	213.57	319.09	477.39
	B	8.222	6.898	8.184	3.306
	$C \times 10^3$	6.141	3.795	4.943	3.956
<i>p</i> -Amino-	A	404.62	149.89	392.28	40.28
	B	8.158	4.477	8.751	6.399
	$C \times 10^3$	5.808	0.643	5.614	1.084

mixed solvents may be due to some structural effects. These effects can arise from either the combined effect of the solvent properties and solvation properties of the ions or the latter property alone in the different solvent mixtures. However, the increasingly negative val-

ues of ΔS° with increasing dioxan content in the mixture might be attributed to (a) enhanced disorder (less structure) in the dioxan-rich solvents so that transfer of 'higher entropy' solvent molecules to the solvation shell occurs, (b) higher order and stronger interactions

TABLE 2 - STANDARD THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES (MOLAL SCALE) FOR THE IONISATION PROCESS OF BENZOIC ACIDS IN WATER* AND DIOXAN-WATER MIXTURES AT 25

Acid	Dioxan wt %	pK_a^m	ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Benzoic	0	4.201	23.97	0.63	78
	10	4.430	25.28	2.74	76
	20	4.533	25.86	2.93	77
	30	5.126	29.25	2.19	91
	40	5.578	31.83	2.02	100
<i>o</i> -Nitro-	0	2.170	12.38		
	10	2.183	12.45	2.27	34
	20	2.283	13.03	2.02	37
	30	2.870	16.37	2.42	47
	40	3.320	18.94	2.20	56
<i>m</i> -Nitro-	0	3.490	19.92	1.59	
	10	3.641	20.77	2.58	61
	20	3.741	21.34	2.23	64
	30	4.340	24.76	2.24	76
	40	4.786	27.31	2.39	84

DASH · THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF IONISATION OF BENZOIC AND SUBSTITUTED BENZOIC *etc.*

Table - 2 (contd.)

<i>p</i> -Nitro-	0	3.442	19.64	0.13	65
	10	3.345	19.08	2.37	56
	20	3.446	19.66	2.25	58
	30	4.042	23.06	1.73	72
	40	4.487	25.60	2.01	79
<i>o</i> -Chloro-	0	2.940	16.77		
	10	3.314	18.91	2.10	56
	20	3.415	19.57	2.29	58
	30	4.008	22.87	2.75	68
	40	4.460	25.45	2.15	78
<i>m</i> -Chloro-	0	3.827	21.84	0.75	76
	10	3.835	21.88	2.73	64
	20	3.941	22.89	1.98	69
	30	4.532	25.86	1.84	81
	40	4.978	28.40	2.09	88
<i>p</i> -Chloro-	0	3.986	22.74	0.96	73
	10	3.980	22.71	2.29	69
	20	4.080	23.28	2.22	71
	30	4.670	26.65	2.04	83
	40	5.123	29.23	1.62	93
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy-	0	2.973	16.96	3.05	46
	10	3.013	17.19	2.26	50
	20	3.109	17.74	2.45	51
	30	4.702	26.83	2.62	81
	40	5.153	29.40	2.38	91
<i>m</i> -Hydroxy-	0	4.080	23.28	0.63	
	10	4.282	24.43	2.25	73
	20	4.381	25.00	2.00	77
	30	4.970	28.36	2.21	88
	40	5.420	30.93	1.68	98
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy-	0	4.582	26.14	2.26	80
	10	4.748	27.09	2.11	84
	20	4.850	27.67	2.11	86
	30	5.440	31.09	2.10	97
	40	5.884	33.57	2.69	104
<i>o</i> -Amino-	0	4.950	28.24		
	10	5.139	29.32	1.90	92
	20	5.238	29.89	2.03	93
	30	5.832	33.28	2.37	104
	40	6.283	35.85	2.26	113

Table - 2 (contd)

<i>m</i> -Amino-	0 ^a	4 750	27 10		
	10	4 948	28 23	2 20	87
	20	5 050	28 81	2 36	89
	30	5 640	32 18	2 30	100
	40	6 087	34 73	2 41	108
<i>p</i> -Amino	0 ^a	4 890	27 90		
	10	5 069	28 92	2 13	90
	20	5 172	29 51	1 78	93
	30	5 761	32 87	2 04	103
	40	6 210	35 43	2 62	110

* Thermodynamic quantities calculated from Ref 12

^aFrom I Gyenes 'Titration in Non-aqueous Media' (Transl by D Cohen and I I Millar) London 1967 p 34

in the solvation region for dioxan-rich solvents so that solvating molecules have lower entropy than in aqueous medium. (c) both (a) and (b) might contribute, or (d) enhanced disorder occurs in both the solvent and in the solvation region when dioxan is present but the enhanced disorder in the solvent as in (a) dominates and therefore ΔS° becomes more negative. Since the net effect of solvent transfer is from bulk solvent to solvation regions around the ions produces a greater disordering effect when dioxan is present which is reflected in more negative ΔS° values.

It is remarkable that in a majority of cases, very considerable changes occur in the thermodynamic functions ΔH° and ΔS° between water and 10 wt % dioxan-water mixture (Table 2) and comparatively little change thereafter as the dioxan content is increased. The irregularity in ΔH° and ΔS° values between water and 10 wt % aqueous dioxan may result from the structural modification of solvation shells of ions due to specific solvation of uncharged acid by dioxan because of very great stoichiometric excess of 10 wt % dioxan by weight containing about 1.1 mol dioxan kg⁻¹ over any solute species in the mixed solvent.

Using the ionic radii for the hydrogen (r_H) and carboxylate ions (r_X) it is possible to estimate the approximate difference of pK_a^m values in the mixed solvents from Born equation¹³

$$\Delta pK_a^m = (pK_a^m - w pK_a^m) = 121.6 (D_s^{-1} - D_w^{-1}) (r_H^{-1} + r_X^{-1})$$

where D_s and D_w are the dielectric constants of the mixed solvent and water respectively and correlate quantitatively with the experimental data. As observed the experimental ΔpK_a^m values in the mixed solvents do not agree with that computed from Born equation. It may be concluded that the overall variation of ΔpK_a^m with solvent composition indicates the significant role of specific solute-solvent interactions.

Experimental

Dioxan (AnalaR) was purified further by the reported method¹⁴. Solvents of various compositions were made up by weight in conductivity water. The dioxan contents of the mixed solvent were accurate within $\pm 0.02\%$. Benzoic and substituted benzoic acids (E. Merck G.R. or B.D.H. L.R.) were purified by the reported methods¹⁵. Potassium salts of these acids were prepared by the method similar to that described elsewhere¹⁶. Potassium chloride (G.R.) was dried at 100° for 2 h. Potassium salts were stored in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride until required.

Preparation of the electrodes, setting up of the cells, e.m.f. measurements and other experimental details have been discussed earlier¹. The reproducibility of the e.m.f. measurements was of the order of ± 0.1 mV. All measurements were made in water thermostats maintained at appropriate temperatures varying within ± 0.1 K.

References

1. R. C. DAS, U. N. DASH and K. N. PANDA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1979, **32**, 301.
2. R. C. DAS, U. N. DASH and K. N. PANDA, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1980, **76**, 2151; U. N. DASH and M. K. MISHRA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1987, **115**, 97; U. N. DASH, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1993, communicated.
3. U. N. DASH, B. B. DAS, U. K. BISWAL, T. PANDA and M. K. MISHRA, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India* 1987 **36**, 173; *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1989, **32**, 191; U. N. DASH, D. Sc. Thesis, Utkal University, 1991.
4. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", Reinhold, New York, 1958, p. 286.
5. R. G. BATES, R. N. ROY and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 905.
6. R. C. DAS, U. N. DASH and K. N. PANDA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1974, **54**, 1916.
7. P. K. DAS and U. C. MISHRA, *Electrochim Acta*, 1977, **22**, 59.
8. G. J. JANZ in "Reference Electrodes", eds. D. J. G. IVES and G. J. JANZ, Academic, London, 1961.
9. R. N. ROY, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 8151.
10. Ref. 4 (first reference) Chaps. 11 and 12.
11. H. S. HARNED and R. A. ROBINSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc* 1940, **36**, 973.
12. J. J. CHRISTENSEN, R. M. IZATT and L. D. HANSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 213; A. ALBERT and F. P. SERJEANT "Ionization Constants of Acids and Bases", Methuen, New York, 1962; T. MAJURI, H. C. KO and L. G. HEPLER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, **52**, 2906.
13. M. BORN, *Z. Phys.*, 1920, **1**, 45.
14. U. N. DASH and M. C. PADHJ, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1982 **85**, 315.
15. A. I. VOGEL, "A Hand Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1960.
16. U. N. DASH and B. NAYAK, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, **25**, 941.

